

often sown in dry soil before flooding) for survival after severe soil and atmospheric drought.

Considerable variation was found in the rices representing a cross section of the hydrologic environments where rice is cultivated (see fig.). Surprisingly, upland rices were less well adapted to the test conditions than were rices from lowland and deep-water regions (see

table). The rices that had high survival rates were from areas prone to seedling-stage drought problems.

Detecting rices from the areas where natural selection has been acting gives confidence in the procedure. A similar procedure is currently used in a greenhouse to screen large numbers of varieties.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Deep water

Deep-water rice workshop

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The Deep-Water Rice Workshop, November 8–10, 1976, in Bangkok, Thailand, sponsored by The International Rice Research Institute (IRRI) in cooperation with the Thailand Ministry of Agriculture and Cooperatives, covered a variety of topics:

- Flowering responses of floating rices
- Morphological, physiological, and anatomical differences of varieties adapted to deep water
- Estimating heritability of elongation ability in crosses between floating

Participants in the 1976 Deepwater Rice Workshop toured the Thailand central plains and saw deep-water experiments in farmers' fields and at the Huntra Rice Experiment Station. Left to right are Dr. P. B. Escuro, FAO rice improvement specialist, Burma; Dr. K. Zan, general manager, Agricultural Research Institute, Burma; and Dr. M. S. Ahmed, plant breeder, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute.

varieties and high yielding semidwarfs

- Seedling height as a predictor of elongation ability if one parent is a floating rice
- A new procedure for rapid development of photoperiod-sensitive deep-water hybrids
- Screening for elongation, distinguishing between seedlings of floating and nonfloating varieties, rapid internode elongation, submergence tolerance, drought tolerance, and kneeing ability
- Nitrogen response of plants with elongation ability
- Yields of new semidwarf hybrids with elongation genes
- Pest management in deep-water rice
- Results from the first International Rice Deep Water Observational Nursery
- National research progress

Recommendations were made for new deep-water rice terminology and a new standard scoring system for measuring elongation ability of deep-water rice.

Determination of the adaptation of rice genotypes to water deeper than 30 cm — a new formula

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A new formula for determining the floating ability or the adaptation to deeper-than-normal water in rice genotypes has been evolved. For better

Two indicators of water-depth adaptability of rice genotypes.

Rice genotype	X_F	F_D
<i>Very high adaptability</i>		
HTA 16-CNB-5	88.79	173.95
OC 1393 (M)-29	86.84	170.21
OC 1393 (M)-88	82.61	170.15
HTA 22-CNB-3	102.65	169.15
<i>High adaptability</i>		
HTA 826-CNB-23	87.83	158.34
HTA 108-CNB-24	75.35	156.19
HTA 448-CNB-16	88.64	145.06
OC 1393	85.38	140.94
<i>Moderately high adaptability</i>		
Pankaj	73.62	134.45
HTA 171-CNB-12	87.37	133.74
HTA 607-CNB-8	81.02	130.18
Pankaj(M)-107	69.38	129.72
Pankaj(M)-86	73.36	129.63
Pankaj(M)-91	73.10	120.50
<i>Low adaptability</i>		
IR442-2-58	62.57	117.97

interpretation of field screening work, it may replace Morishima's 1974 formula, at least in situations where water rises to 90 cm. Morphological data were taken from 15 rice genotypes grown at normal (up to 10 cm) and above-normal (up to 90 cm) water depths in fields at the Rice Research Station, Chinsurah (West Bengal) in 1975 kharif (wet season). Morishima's X_F values and the authors' F_D values showed wide differences. Field observations tallied closer with the latter. A scale for interpreting the values classifies the genotypes into four groups: very high (F_D 140–159), moderate (F_D 120–139), and low (F_D below 120) adaptation to increasing water depths (see table).

The suggested formula for calculating F_D is: $A + 0.5B + 0.2C + D - 0.25E$
Where:

F_D = floating ability or adaptation to deeper-than-normal water.

A = number of internodes longer than 3 cm;

B = final height with deeper-than-normal water;

C = total increase in stem length;

D = total increase in stem length from sowing until 81 days later;

$E = \frac{C}{\text{stem elongation of normally grown plants}} \times 100$